

Observing Islamic Banking Research Around the World; A Bibliometric Review 2013-2023

Akmal¹

Abstract

The banking theme is of great interest in Islamic economic studies. Research that carries this theme is most dominant because finance and Islamic banking (IB) are the initial discourses of Islamic economics that introduce the mudharabah system as the antithesis of usurious finance and banking (Siddique 2022) . Academically, Islamic banking has its own appeal compared to other themes in Islamic economics scientific discourse, both in terms of theme and methodology (Tumewang 2023; Mubarik and Saeed 2022) . The Journal of Islamic Finance and Banking has emerged since 1985, 1989, published by (Mayer 1985; Ahmed 1989) . Until now, based on Scopus data, the number of research publications with the title IB and sharia banking over the past 10 years has reached 989 publications indexed by the Scopus base. This number does not include publications outside Scopus. In fact, IB research is one of the growing trends in Islamic economic research.

Islamic banking, bibliometrics

INTRODUCTION

Over the past three years (2021-2023), IB research in the form of research, reviews, and bibliometrics has been published with research coverage covering several categories. First, research on IB network metrics and growth in various countries (Hassanein and Mostafa 2023; Abd. Wahab et al. 2023) . Second, IB research method metrics (Tijjani et al. 2021; Gira and Labidi 2021; Mubarik and Saeed 2022; Salami, Tanrivermiş, and Abubakar 2022) . Three, review of major obstacles in implementing IB (Ali et al. 2023) . Four, development, conceptual structure, and thematic of IB research indexed by WOS which is isolated globally but isolated by limited networks (Hassanein and Mostafa 2023) . Five, IB research streams in several countries, Bangladesh and Indonesia, and how IB in Turkey as a Scopus indexed research topic (Muhammad Kabir Hassan, Hudaefi, and Agung 2022; M Kabir Hassan et al. 2023; Islam et al. 2022) . Six, IB efficiency and performance metrics (Ikra et al. 2021; Shah, Sukmana, and Fianto 2021; Maradin, Suljić Nikolaj, and Olgić Draženović 2021; Pambuko and Sriyana 2023) , seven, supervisory board competency and maqasid sharia modeling as an index of IB measurement sustainability (Ammar, Rebai, and Saidane 2022; Basit 2023) .

The research scope has given us quite extensive information, about methods, networks, themes, IB performance in various regions through bibliometric methods and future implications. However, there has been no bibliometric research that integrates IB with regions around the world. The scope of IB research is still local, such as Indonesia and Baghdad (Muhammad Kabir Hassan, Hudaefi, and Agung 2022; M Kabir Hassan et al.

¹ E-mail. akmal@iainkendari.ic.id

2023) . Furthermore, we imagine that each region has a different character where researchers contextualize the locus of IB research. The context includes Southeast Asia, South Asia, the Middle East, Africa and Europe. These regions are widespread in the global world. Therefore, the gap between this research and similar research in the last 3 years is to expand the context of IB research that has been published by researchers in various countries, aiming to map topics, themes, methods, paradigms based on IB research areas around the world and their implications in the future.

METHOD

This study follows the steps of bibliometric research that has been carried out. (Kuzior and Sira 2022; Shi et al. 2021) . Scopus is used to search for IB research documents. Document searches use the keywords "Islamic and banking". Exact words consist of 4 words "Islamic banking", "Islamic bank", dual banking and 'dual banking system. The documents used have a time limit for research publications for the last 10 years 2013-2023.

Table 1. Document search limitations based on time and keywords

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TITLE-ABS-KEY ( islamic AND banking ) AND PUBYEAR > 2012 AND PUBYEAR < 2024 AND ( LIMIT-TO ( EXACTKEYWORD , "Islamic Banking" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTKEYWORD , "Islamic Banks" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTKEYWORD , "Islamic Bank" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTKEYWORD , "Dual Banking" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTKEYWORD , "Dual Banking System" )
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Scopus search data source

IB research publication types include article 1,234, Conference paper 64, Book chapter 63, Review 40, Book, 3, Editorial 2 publications. Based on scopus research, the total documents during 2014-2023 amounted to 1406 documents.

Document mapping includes research index, title, author, academic institution, regional distribution, and language for 10 years. Furthermore, the results of document search using RIS document type, were analyzed using vosviewer software and Microsoft Excel. VoSViewer software is used to determine research trends that include, title, Journal name, academic background, country and institution distribution, output distribution in subject categories, top authors, top citations, and publication trends from 2012 to 2023, using the Visualization of Similarity (VOS) algorithm as an alternative to multidimensional analytics (Ninkov, Frank, and Maggio 2022) .

Chart 1. Illustration of bibliometric research methods (in search of data analysis)

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RESEARCH DATA

I. IB Research Positions Worldwide

1. Growth of IB publications worldwide (2014-2023)

The number of IB research publications in the last 10 years (2012-2023) can be seen in graph I.

Chart 1. Growth of IB research publications worldwide 2012-2023

Scopus search data source

In the last ten years, there were 1406 IB research publications worldwide. IB research growth (2014-2023) averaged % in the last 10 years. The average IB research publication reached 140.6 per year from 2014-2023. In 2014, the number of IB research publications

was only 60 documents. This number continues to increase even though the annual data is very fluctuating. The most research was in 2020, amounting to 200 publications. The growth of IB research after 2020 actually decreased as seen in graph 1.

2. IB research trends by author

Table 1. Shows data on the 10 most productive IB researchers throughout 2014-2023 as follows:

IB researcher ranking top 10 table 2014-2023

NO	NAME	RESEARCH AMOUNT
1	Hassan, M.K.	27
2	Tabash, MI	10
3	Hussainey, K	10
4	Hassan, R.	10
5	Safiullah, M.	9
6	Kassim, S.	9
7	Disli, M.	9
8	Aysan, A.F.	9
9	Ali, M.	9
10	Worthington, A.C.	8

Scopus research data source

Table 1 data shows that Hassan MK is the most productive researcher with 27 research publications related to the keyword IB. Following the names Tabash, MI Hussainey, K., and Hassan, R. With a total of 10 document publications. Next are Safiullah, M. Kassim, S. Disli, M. Aysan, AF Ali, M. , each with 9 publications and Worthington, AC with 8 publications. In addition to the 10 names mentioned in the top 10 researchers based on IB research publications, overall there are 160 names who published IB-themed research throughout 2014-2023. These researchers are spread across a number of regions throughout the world.

3. Distribution of IB research by institutional/academic affiliation worldwide

If IB research is mapped based on the researcher's institutional or university affiliation, there are 160 affiliates spread throughout the world. Almost all of these affiliates are educational institutions except for 2 banking institution affiliates, namely Al-Rayan Bank and Bank Indonesia. The distribution of IB research based on institutional affiliation will only be displayed based on the top 10 as seen in the following graph 2:

Chart 2. IB research affiliates worldwide

Number of Publications

Based on chart 2. the 1st rank of the top 10 IB research distribution worldwide is affiliated with the International Islamic University Malaysia with 102 publications. Next, Universiti Malaya 58 publications, Universiti Utara Malaysia 54 publications, International Islamic University Malaysia 54 publications, INCEIF University 50 publications, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia 39 publications, Universiti Teknologi MARA 38 publications, University of New Orleans 34 publications, Universiti Putra Malaysia 27 publications, Universiti Sains Malaysia 25 publications. Based on these data, most IB research is affiliated with universities in Malaysia. Next we will see the IB research map by country.

based on institutions/universities from 2014-2023 can be seen based on the academic background of researchers, 20% of them have a general academic background. This can be seen from their home base of assignments consisting of Australia, England, the Netherlands and France. While 80 percent of them have a background in Islamic universities. This academic background has shown that the interest in Islamic banking research is still local and in demand by insiders. In the discourse of science, Islamic banking studies are still relatively less dynamic and less developed by outsiders. Researchers with a background in general educational institutions, connect Islamic banking with intellectual capital which is a policy in the development of Islamic banking (Nathan 2007) .

4. Distribution of IB Research by country affiliation worldwide

If IB research is connected to country affiliation, then there are 88 countries affiliated with IB research worldwide for the past 10 years. However, only 20 countries will have their data visualized as in Figure 3 below:

Figure 3 IB research by country affiliation worldwide

Data sources are processed from Scopus search

As with IB research affiliations with institutions predominantly located in Malaysia, the most productive country in IB research is also Malaysia with 456 publications. Next, Indonesia is in second place with 243 publications. Next, Pakistan has 131 publications, the United Kingdom has 124 publications, Saudi Arabia has 101 publications, Tunisia has 90 publications, the United States has 76 publications, the United Arab Emirates has 72 publications, Turkey has 67 publications, Australia has 64 publications, Bangladesh has 43 publications, France has 40 publications, Bahrain has 35 publications, Jordan has 33 publications, India has 29 publications, Qatar has 27 publications, Russian Federation has 21 publications, Nigeria has 20 publications, Iran has 20 publications, and Oman has 19 publications.

Based on the distribution of the number of IB articles indexed by Scopus for 10 years (2013-2023), Muslim countries have the highest percentage of IB research. Although in Western countries IB research has also been found in the last 10 years, the scale is still relatively small. The country with the largest number of IB research is Sudan with 76 articles published. Followed by Pakistan, Malaysia and India. Indonesia as the country with the largest Muslim population in the world is still below Malaysia in IB research. The lack of IB research conducted by researchers in Indonesia is partly due to the relatively slow development of Islamic banking. Even Islamic banking in Indonesia was only established in 1994 under the name Bank Islam Muamalat. Although currently Islamic banking in Indonesia is still trying to reach a potential market in society, through government policies.

5. Distribution of IB research by publisher worldwide

There are 160 journals publishing IB research worldwide (2014-2023). Here is the data for the 20 journals sorted by the highest number of publications:

IB Research Publisher Journal Graph 2014-2023

Based on graph 4, it can be seen that the journal that publishes the most Ib research publications is the Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research with 101 publications. Next, International Journal Of Islamic And Middle Eastern Finance And Management with 87 publications, Journal Of Islamic Marketing with 70 publications, Journal Of Islamic Monetary Economics And Finance with 34 publications, Banks And Bank Systems with 25 publications, Pacific Basin Finance Journal with 24 publications, Isra International Journal Of Islamic Finance with 23 publications, Lecture Notes In Networks And Systems with 20 publications, Journal Of King Abdulaziz University Islamic Economics with 18 publications, Journal Of International Financial Markets Institutions And Money with 17 publications, Journal Of Asian Finance Economics And Business with 17 publications, Qualitative Research In Financial Markets with 14 publications, International Journal Of Finance And Economics with 13 publications, Contributions To Management Science with 13 publications, Advanced Science Letters with 13 publications, International Journal Of Applied Business And Economic Research with 12 publications, Economic Modelling with 12 publications, Jurnal Pengurusan with 11 publications, Humanomics with 11 publications, and Academy Of Accounting And Financial Studies Journal as many as 11 publications.

6. Publications by language

There are 10 language uses in IB research publications. Which language is dominantly used in IB research publications 2014-2023? Of course English, because the international consensus requires it as the main language of international academic conversation. The use of language in research reports can be seen in Figure 3 below:

Languages English 1,376, Arabic 9, Russian 7, Spanish 3, Malay 3, Indonesian 3, French 2, Turkish 1, Persian 1, Italian 1, German 1, Bosnian 1.

II. Viewer data analysis

Based on the comparison of data from the vosviewer software, we can see further how the IB research topics, mainstream topics, collaborations between researchers in various countries, and the topics discussed are related.

1. The interconnectedness of IB topics with other topics

The results of creating 989 documents with the Ris type on the software produced a visualization of IB research for the last 10 years, related to certain terms, which can be seen in (Figure 2) below:

Collaboration between IB researchers around the world can be seen based on the following viewer visualization.

4. Less talked about topic

III. FINDINGS

Based on the discussion above, the findings of this study are:

1. IB research has become a global academic discourse, but its concentration is still local.
2. IB researchers are predominantly from South Asia, the Middle East and Southeast Asia. The context of IB research worldwide is concentrated in South Asia, the Middle East and Southeast Asia.
3. There are 46 topics on IB research worldwide, the largest of which are IB topics on banking systems, products, and adoption.
4. An under-researched topic is performance.

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